

New locality records for the white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT

The white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) has been recorded throughout South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from West Africa, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Angola, Sudan to South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described and photographs of live specimens are provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Firmicus* was described by Simon, 1895 with *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) as the type species. The genus is represented by 19 species and subspecies, of which 16 are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2021).

Firmicus bragantinus is an African endemic species described by Brito Capello, 1866 as *Thomisus bragantinus*. The species was then transferred by Lessert (1919) to *Synaema bragantinum* and again by Roewer (1955) to *F. bragantinus*.

The general morphology of the species is provided based on live specimens. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. Requests were also made for photographs of species for the SANSA Virtual Museum and sets of photographs of *F. bragantinus* have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Firmicus bragantinus (Brito Capello, 1866)

Thomisus bragantinus Brito Capello, 1866: 86

Synaema bragantinum Lessert, 1919: 195; Lessert, 1928: 320; Lessert, 1933: 121, f. 37; Lessert, 1936: 260, f. 54-55

Firmicus bragantinus Roewer, 1955: 833.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Firmicus bragantinus* can be recognised by its slightly flattened body. The female is white, with distinct dark patterns on the body and legs (Fig. 1). Carapace is pale cream; anterior eye row is straight, with eyes equidistantly spaced; posterior eye row is recurved; anterior lateral eyes are slightly larger than others (Fig. 2); chelicerae has black spots. Abdomen is white, with black spots and transverse lines. Legs are white, with black spots, and black bands at legs joints; two front pairs longer than posterior pairs. Male is smaller in size, carapace orange-brown; abdomen with brown scutum with two pairs of black spots; front legs with femora and trochanters dark, rest of legs paler. Size: Total length: female and male 4-5 mm.

Figures 1-3. *Firmicus bragantinus*. 1. Female dorsal view. 2. Female anterior view. 3. Male dorsal view. Photo credits 1-2. V van der Walt 3. Robin Lyle.

Figures 4-5. *Firmicus bragantinus*. 4. Female epigyne ventral view. 5. Male palp ventral view. Photo credits Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Angola, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, South Africa and Sudan.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Hluhluwe Hippo Pools (-28.02, 32.28). **Limpopo:** Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Kapama Private Game Reserve (-24.43, 31.03); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 0.25). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-32.02, 31.08); Mbombela (-25.47, 30.96); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Ngwenya Lodge (-25.38, 31.85). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve.

Figure 6. South African records of *Firmicus bragantinus*.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs and herbs. They are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. They are usually sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savannah biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Firmicus bragantinus is mainly active during the day, moving around on vegetation (Figs 7 & 8). The adults are abundant in the summer months, while the juveniles overwinter low in plant bases. They prey on a variety of small invertebrates that come within grasping distance. They have been sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus and grapefruit orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 7. *Firmicus bragantinus* female sampled from Kapama in Limpopo. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 8. *Firmicus bragantinus* female sampled from Ngwenya Lodge in Mpumalanga. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION

In South Africa, the species is recorded from four provinces and it is found in seven protected areas: Kruger National Park, Sodwana Bay National Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009). No conservation actions are recommended. Due to its wide range and no known threats, it is listed as Least Concern.

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